

Indigenous Wisdom: How African Religious Practices Drive Entrepreneurship Success in Hwange District, Zimbabwe

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Abstract

Case Studies

This study looks at how African Indigenous Religious practices (AIRPs) impact the success of entrepreneurship in Hwange district, Zimbabwe. AIRs practices have been a big part of many African communities' culture for a long time, shaping people's values, behaviors, and ways of making decisions. The authors of this article are familiar with the Shona culture in Zimbabwe which was the main point of reference for African Indigenous Religious Practices in their study. Literature demonstrates, however, that while the Shona may differ from other ethnic groups, the process is essentially the same and the results may be transferred to other ethnicities with only minor variations. The article sought to answer the question on how African religious practices impact entrepreneurship success in Zimbabwe. A mixed-methods approach was used in this study to give a deep understanding of the lived experiences and points of view of the local business community. It does this by interviewing entrepreneurs, religious leaders, and other community leaders and opinion makers in the society. Questionnaires were also distributed to gather the general views of the people who are in business and their experience. Snowballing sampling was used to reach 210 participants. The findings indicate that there is much to be gained from this extensive religious tradition as it has a significant impact on entrepreneurship success.

Keywords: African Indigenous Religious Practices, Entrepreneurship Success, Nhimbe Model, Culture, Economic Development, Hwange.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship has become a significant driver of economic development and prosperity in many countries of the world, including Africa. Hwange district in Zimbabwe, has a rich cultural heritage that includes a broad array of African traditional religious practices. These traditional belief systems and rituals have long been an intrinsic component of the local community's way of life. However, the possible impact of these African indigenous religious traditions (AIRs) on entrepreneurship success in the region has received minimal scholarly study. This study analyzes the impact of African indigenous religious practices on entrepreneurship success in Hwange district. Understanding this dynamic provides useful

insights into the interplay between cultural characteristics and business performance, which can drive policies and actions to foster entrepreneurship in the region.

Hwange district is located in the western region of Zimbabwe. This region is renowned for its varied cultural legacy, characterized by a prominent prevalence of African traditional religious customs. These conventional belief systems frequently encompass the reverence of ancestral spirits, the utilization of ancient healing techniques, and the adherence to diverse rites and ceremonies. Hwange is inhabited by diverse ethnic groups, which includes, Tonga, Nambya, Ndebele, Shona, and several more smaller groups who speak distinct languages.

As individual ethnic groups that are interconnected, their belief systems exhibit minimal divergence. The Shona people constitute the predominant ethnic group in Zimbabwe, comprising around 80% of the total population (Mangena, 2023). Their extensive cultural legacy encompasses a wide range of customs, beliefs, and rituals that are firmly grounded in their historical background and perspective. The Shona people are not a singular, homogeneous population, but rather consist of various subgroups, including the Karanga, Zezuru, Korekore, and the Manyika, as well as the Ndau, a related group that was, until 2013, considered Shona (Constitution of Zimbabwe, 2013). Each subgroup has its own unique languages and cultural characteristics. The Ndebele people, who originated from South Africa, are the second most populous ethnic group in Zimbabwe. They migrated to Zimbabwe throughout the 19th century. They possess a robust cultural identity. The Ndebele people possess an intricate ethnic identity, which has been influenced by their relationships with the Kalanga people (Msindo, 2012). The majority of the Tonga population emigrated from Zambia to Zimbabwe (Hambulo, Muleya, and Letseka, 2023). The Tonga inhabit several regions in southern Africa, such as some parts of Zimbabwe, Zambia, and Mozambique. In Zimbabwe, they possess distinct language and cultural customs, which may exhibit certain resemblances to other ethnic groups in the area. However, establishing precise relationships would necessitate further comprehensive investigation. The Tonga people have been subjected to marginalization within the Zimbabwean school system, resulting in adverse effects on their language, culture, and identity (Hang'ombe and Mumpande, 2020). The Nambya are thought to have originated from Great Zimbabwe in Masvingo, establishing a significant connection with the Shona or Karanga people (Pikirayi, Shenjere-Nyabezi, and Sagiya, 2022). The Nambya people constitute one of Zimbabwe's minor ethnic groupings, predominantly situated in the north-western region of the country. The Nambya who are largely domiciled in north-western Zimbabwe share strong affiliations with others in the Zimbabwean culture, especially encompassing the Shona (Shenjere-Nyabezi and

Gronenborn, 2021). The languages, cultures, and history of the Shona, Tonga, Nambya, and the Ndebele in Zimbabwe are interconnected and are further strengthened by intermarriage.

Prior research indicates that cultural influences can exert a substantial impact on entrepreneurial attitudes, practices, and outcomes. Several studies in the African environment have explored the influence of traditional values, beliefs, and practices on the success of entrepreneurs. Nevertheless, the precise impact of traditional religious traditions on entrepreneurship achievement in Hwange has not been thoroughly investigated. This study aimed to fill the research gap by examining the potential connections between African indigenous religious practices and business outcomes in Hwange. The results of this study may enhance the comprehension of the intricate interaction of cultural, social, and economic elements in the realm of entrepreneurship advancement.

One of the common sayings in Shona philosophy and wisdom is the advice to take good care of what you have because it is widely believed that *chawawana batisisa, midzimu haiipi kaviri* (hold fast to what you have because the ancestral spirits do not give twice), which echoes the English adage, "Fortune knocks once on everyone's door." This maxim falls within the socio-religious category since it emphasizes the need for caution when managing possession because ancestors only offer gifts once. Therefore, it requires that one behaves in a way that promotes the expansion of the business rather than in any other way.

The Shona also adhere to a *catenae* or chain mentality, according to which children must be taught the fundamentals of commercial success and sustainability at a young age because they believe that, *dehwe rinopetwa richiri nyoro* (the skin/hide is folded while it is still wet). This implies that commercial success training needs to be inculcated by parents in their children while children they are still young. It is assumed that *mbudzi kudya mufenje hufananyina* (a goat feeds on the *mufenje* tree just like its mother). This means that a child will usually follow its parents' footsteps. In

business, this tells us that when a parent is doing business the children will learn from her/him and will also do likewise. The emphasis is on modeling what one wants his children to do not only telling them what is right. The aforementioned makes it evident that AIRs place a strong emphasis on the value of building and maintaining social capital because it is a crucial component of entrepreneurship, viability, and sustainability. The Shona saying *sango rinopa waneta* (the forest gives those who are tiring) which encourages one to keep on working hard because those that persevere ultimately get the rewards. These sayings give courage, focus and an impetus to those who are about to give up in whatever they are doing because of challenges. The encouragement simply means people should not give up. *Kufa kwemurume hubudaura* (Aman is only considered mortally wounded when his intestines are out) is another axiom that encourages one to keep pushing and working hard. This means when you still have a breath in you, you keep on fighting. People are encouraged never to give up. The African Indigenous religious practice and philosophy also encourages people to always try new things. This is reflected in the proverb, *Zvirozvi dzwachembereyeka Chiviyakabikama bweakabudamuto* (Things need to be tried out, an elderly lady from Chivi cooked stones and had some broth). This means that people should always innovate as this is the backbone of entrepreneurship and success. The article continues by way of reviewing what other authors say about the impact of African Indigenous Religious practices on business success.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section seeks to answer a question of how African religious practices influence entrepreneurship success in Zimbabwe. Since African Indigenous religious practices are a drill rather than a set of rules described in a book, there is not much information about it in the literature (Maviya, Ngorora-Madzimure and Mapara, 2023). The majority of customs are passed down orally and via experience. However, only a few writers have begun to recognize the beneficial effects that African religious practices have on entrepreneurship and

have begun to record the ancient traditions. African Indigenous Religion is seen as evil because missionaries during the colonial era thought African customs were strange and old-fashioned (Mokhutso, 2022). Studies show that honoring ancestors in African customs is not demonic, and the idea of demons is not part of African culture (Nweke, 2022). New research stresses that it is true to its roots as an ethnic religion (Balcomb, 2021). African ontology talks about a Supreme Being, gods, and spirits, and relatives are very important even in business and in how people live (Mwangi and Mwakio, 2021). Few people have openly practiced this religion because they are afraid of becoming victims and are considered to be backward. Many Africans have been observed practicing this religion, albeit behind closed doors. The foundation of African Indigenous religious practices among the Bantu is *sunhu/ubuntu*, where ideas like *nhimbe* (work parties) first appeared. *Nhimbe* has implications on the economy, society, politics, and religion (Mahohoma and Muzambi, 2021). *Nhimbe*, the idea of supporting one another in various business activities such as agriculture, is deeply ingrained in the Shona culture, where it is considered the norm, to assist others who would have invited the community to assist with agricultural labour such as cultivation or harvesting so that, they might succeed in ensuring food security. This practice is an essential indigenous one that is inextricably linked to African Traditional Religion. *Nhimbe* is regarded as one of the communal rites (Bohwasi, 2020). Some scholars concur that *nhimbe* is carried out to aid the entrepreneur. Although *nhimbe* is a common practice among the Shona, scholarship shows that it is widely practiced in several African cultures and nations. It goes by different names, for instance, *ilima* among the Ndebele of Zimbabwe, and *harambee* among the Gikuyu in Kenya. *Chilimbais* is the name that is used among the Bemba in Zambia, while the term *letsemain* among the Pedi, Sotho South Africa and the Tswana of South Africa and Botswana (Sithole, 2020). This practice is now also used as an informal credit and savings scheme. This shows that among the various ethnicities and regions of Africa, indigenous religious practices are almost identical.

However, ensuring household food security is the primary goal of the *thenhimbe* practice in any Zimbabwean society (Sithole, 2020).

The primary goal of Shona entrepreneurship is to benefit the community as a whole, not just the individual. This is demonstrated by customs like *kuronzera*, which provides people without cattle with animals to utilize and milk. The Shona culture really advocates *kuronzera* as part of their practice to help the upcoming entrepreneur with labor capital rather than selling the milk or renting out cattle to utilize for ploughing. It is grounded in Shona wisdom as encapsulated in the proverb *huru ingokudzwa ngewayo* (One is respected and promoted by his/her kith and kin). This statement emphasizes people not do it alone but they should work as a community or group to accomplish more and this is possible by helping one another.

In the African, specifically Shona culture, apprenticeship is a common way to teach children how to run a business most commonly, crop farming and animal husbandry. This is also clear from a Ghanaian perspective where it was also noted that Ghanaian culture, and by extension sub-Saharan African culture, heavily influences entrepreneurship. The majority of the influence was shown to have a favorable impact on entrepreneurship (Darley and Blankson, 2020). The Shona practice and ritual of *dendo* or *bira*, a traditional thanksgiving ceremony that enables underprivileged members of the community to benefit from and share in the successes of nearby successful individuals entrepreneurs, demonstrates how strongly Shona culture and practice support and encourage entrepreneurship (Bohwasi, 2020). This has developed into a culture and practice that demonstrates how the components of entrepreneurship are ingrained in fulfilling community commitments and creating an identity. The lack of commercialization in Shona culture makes it difficult to see the macro-input that entrepreneurship contributes to the nation, but it has always existed and has been sustaining communities all along. This is noted in the fact that African Indigenous Religions (AIRs) are different from scriptural religions because they focus on rituals instead

of beliefs and on society over individuality (Beek, 2020). African indigenous ways of managing money, which come from the Ubuntu mindset, put the well-being of the group ahead of individual gain (Ojera, 2018). This focus on the community has an effect on the mental and physical health of people in Africa (Ohajunwa, 2021) and builds a groundswell of support for the business.

Literature demonstrates that entrepreneurship existed in the African and Shona society long before colonialism and westernization and that there are customs and religious practices that are associated with it. Even though these methods vary depending on the location of Africa, they nonetheless demonstrate how successful African indigenous religious practices had their own unique approach to addressing entrepreneurship. How entrepreneurship was defined by individuals who undertake African indigenous religious practices and how entrepreneurship is understood now using western standards may differ. This makes it so challenging to measure the success of entrepreneurship. The African indigenous religious practices are more community-based, whilst the norms of the West are more individualistic. The idea of *zunderamambo*, or traditional social welfare in Zimbabwe, lends support to this. The Shona word *zunde* can refer to a sizable group of individuals engaged in a common activity or a significant quantity of grain that has been kept for use by members of a community (Stathers, Sibanda and Chigariro, 2000). Here, all of the community's physically fit individuals collaborate to provide food for the elderly, disabled, and orphans. In times of drought and adversity, it was traditionally a crucial part of village food security (Gwakwa, 2017). The idea of *zunderamambo*, also known as the chief's granary, was a social community entrepreneurship designed to always ensure food security (Dhemba, Gumbo and Nyamusara, 2002; Mararike, 2001). Chiefs typically used this *zunderamambo* social community entrepreneurship model as a food security mechanism. This demonstrates how crucial entrepreneurship is to the indigenous African religious traditions. Additionally, *madzimambo* (chiefs) are responsible for

safeguarding African Indigenous religious customs in their localities. This demonstrates that entrepreneurship is not only supported but also exercised for the community's good.

Some literature states that people today cannot construct a new modern African society unless they find themselves, their roots, and heritage, and embrace all that helped their predecessors survive, thrive, and be successful in creating a dynamic society in the past (Rukuni, 2007). The history of the *dendo* (Thanksgiving ceremony) should be considered. This demonstrates how prosperous the population was at the time. What gave them their success? How were their operations going? Trying to do business in a Western manner without taking into account indigenous business practices may be the cause of less success in entrepreneurship in Zimbabwe. The African indigenous religious practices are intertwined with daily life. The way individuals live and conduct business is inextricably linked to the profession and the community at large.

Business, religion, environmental protection, and maintaining harmony in the community are all included in the practice. As a result, entrepreneurship is not just entrepreneurship but also a planned, directed activity.

METHODS

This research utilized a mixed-methods approach to examine the influence of religious practices on entrepreneurship performance in Hwange District, Zimbabwe. Nassè's (2020) writings informed the decision to employ a mixed-methods approach, emphasizing the significance of integrating qualitative and quantitative methods to enhance the comprehension of religious identity and its impact on behavior, particularly in the context of initiating or expanding a business for this study. Stausberg (2021) underscores the importance of a pluralistic methodology in examining various research methodologies within the field of religion. The researchers employed snowball sampling to pick two hundred and ten entrepreneurs from Hwange District as a representative sample. Subsequently, 70 entrepreneurs were picked

from each of the three major religious groups: Christianity, African Indigenous religions, and Islam, to guarantee a representative sample. Seventy people were selected from each group using a snowball sampling method, wherein members referred one another. The sample size was determined based on the criteria set forth by Jeyaseelan (1989) and Gogtay (2010), emphasizing the need to balance statistical and practical considerations. A minimum sample size of 100 participants is typically deemed sufficient for quantitative research (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970), but Mumtaz et al. (2020) advocate for a minimum of 200 participants. This study aimed to enhance statistical power and accuracy by selecting a sample size of 210, exceeding the minimum criterion. Structured questionnaires were employed to gather quantitative data regarding the demographic features of the three religious practices. Extensive interviews were performed with 20 entrepreneurs from the original sample of 210. This expanding selection aimed to reduce researcher bias in participant selection. The study emphasized the importance of snowball sampling to mitigate biases in data collection, as noted by Xiong (2020). Rigorous sampling techniques were established and systematic instruments to guarantee the authenticity and reliability of the data. Regression analysis was utilized to analyze quantitative data with SPSS statistical software. The regression models examined the correlation between the independent variable (African religious practices, Islam and Christianity) and various success indicators for entrepreneurs, including firm survival, profitability, growth, and financial success. The researchers employed thematic analysis on the qualitative data from the interviews to identify recurring themes and narratives. The study complied with ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants and ensuring the confidentiality of their responses. The snowballing selection of interviewees mitigated prejudice and guaranteed equitable representation of diverse experiences and perspectives about the impact of African religious traditions on economic success in Hwange District.

RESULTS

CATEGORY	DETAILS
Quantitative data	
Total participants	210 Individuals
Age distribution	18-25 years 34.5% 26-35 years 24.3% 36-45 years 18.7% 46 & above 22.5%
Unemployment rates	95 of young people in Zimbabwe not employed
Employment sectors	Nearly 90% of workers are employed in the informal sector
Gender distribution	Female : 55.95% Male : 43.57% Other genders : 0.48%
Impact of African Indigenous religion Practices	No significant effect on entrepreneurship success ($\beta = 0.176, p > 0.05$) Qualitative data: Positive impact on decision-making, values, resilience and courage
Qualitative data	
CATEGORY	
DETAILS	
Total participants	30 individuals
Age distribution	18-25 years (6.67%), 26-35 years (26.67%) 36-45 years (19.99%), 46 & above (46.67%)
Motivation factors	Poverty, family background, future job possibilities
Impact of ARIs on entrepreneurship	ARIs inspire entrepreneurs, give good values, give courage to soldier on in a difficulty environment,

Qualitative data

The total participants were 30 individuals 10 from each religion represented. The age distribution 18-25 years was 6.67%, while age from 26-35 years was 26.67%, 36-45 years were 19.99% and 46 and above were 46.67%. The motivation factor cited by participants was poverty, family background, future job possibilities and survival. Three different religions participated in this study, different people from different religions mentioned different things on how AIRs impact the success of entrepreneurship in the Hwange region. Though their responses were different most of them showed that AIRs indirectly impact success of entrepreneurship by encouraging people to stay focused and resilience. The proverb *kufakwemurumehubudaura*, (A man is only considered mortally wounded when his intestines are out) was mentioned by an elderly man who was

showing how the saying of the elders who passed on long ago gives power to people in their doings. He stated that these saying are rooted in the African religious practices. Qualitative statistics also showed how important community and working together are in African Indigenous practices. The adage, *Charachimwehachitswanyinda* (one finger cannot crush a louse) was also mentioned. It emphasizes that communities are spaces where people depend on each other in life. This makes it easier for people to start their own businesses because they can use shared information, resources, and networks. They can even get assistance and guidance from those that started earlier.

Discussion

The results provide a comprehensive overview of the demographic characteristics and key business-

related attributes of the study participants, which comprised a total of 210 individuals. Regarding age distribution, the respondents spanned a wide range, with the largest proportion falling between the ages of 18 to 25 years (34.5%), followed by those aged 26 to 35 years (24.3%). The results show the highest figure of young people being motivated to start businesses which could be caused by a number of factors, among them; poverty, family background, and future job possibilities (Kabonga, Zvokumba and Borz, 2021). Due to high unemployment rates of up to 95% of most young people in Zimbabwe are out of work. However, youth businesses have grown in the country (Mazikana, Peku, Sifile and Mudziso, 2019). Nearly 90% of workers are now employed in the informal sector (Mujeyi and Sadomba, 2019).

Quantitative data shows that African Indigenous religion practices did not have a significant effect on how the success of entrepreneurship ($\beta = -0.176, p > 0.05$). But the qualitative results showed that African Indigenous Religious practices had an impact on the success of entrepreneurs' ways of thinking, making decisions, and running their businesses in a way that is based on their values. This was also supported by the research done by Gursoy, Altinay and Kenebayeva, (2017), who asserted that African traditions have a positive impact on the way business is done. People who participated in the study and followed African religious indigenous practices said that these practices helped them stay focused, to be strong, and to be very dedicated to their job. People thought that their cultural values give them the strength to deal with problems and run their business in an honest way. The axiom, *kufakwemurumehubudaurawas* mentioned as an encouragement statement which emanate from AIRs which gives people power not to stop even if the situation is hard. These sayings which are deeply rooted in African Indigenous religious practices and wisdom, stressed how important it is to keep going, being creative, and being open to change. It was seen that business owners who use these techniques often come up with new ideas, make the most of limited resources, and meet specific local needs. This made their companies more successful in the long run and improves their reputation. The Hunhu/Ubuntu

attitude, which stresses doing the right thing, affects how people in rural Shona communities run their businesses (Konyana, 2013).

The qualitative statistics also showed how important community and working together are in African Indigenous practices, as echoed in the saying, *Charachimwehachitswanyinda*. Communities where people depend on each other make it easier for people to start their own businesses because they can use shared information, resources, and networks. African Indigenous Religious practices affect how entrepreneurs act, who they are, what they believe and are often used as a way to deal with money problems. The study also found that African Indigenous religious practices have an indirect impact on business, as it inspires business people, and give people ways to deal with tough economic times. The same results were supported by Namatovu, Dawa, Adewale and Mulira (2018). Other research also supports these findings by mentioning the AIRs' indirect impact, business by affecting how people think about risk, how they handle their inventory, and how well their businesses do (Butindaet, al., 2023). As seen in Senegalese local economic development projects are driven by spiritual villages (Cochrane, 2012). Spirituality is often a part of business and work in West Africa, which affects how resources are used and how money is made (Swindell, 2019).

The use of both quantitative and qualitative data together helped the researchers to understand how African Indigenous religious practices affect the success of entrepreneurs in a broader sense. This research refutes unfavorable assumptions and raises the possibility that attitudes toward work ethics may be favorably influenced by convictions about the potential profitability of indigenous African religious practices. Rukuni (2007) observes that one cannot construct a new modern African civilization today unless they find themselves, the origins, and the heritage and embrace everything that allowed their predecessors to survive, grow, and be successful in creating a dynamic society in the past.

Conclusion

The study's findings indicate that AIRs have no direct substantial influence on overall

entrepreneurship performance; rather it has an indirect impact in influencing the success of entrepreneurship. These findings indicate that the success of entrepreneurship can be affected by a range of factors, such as individual characteristics, the availability of resources, and the current economic climate. AIRs were discovered to have an indirect beneficial impact on the success of entrepreneurship; these include but are not limited to faithfulness in business dealings, character (*ubuntu*), resilience, patience, and other attributes which are influenced by cultural and religious practices. Some of the Shona sayings function as catalysts to encourage people to persevere such as the saying which says *sangorinopawaneta* whose meaning was unpacked earlier. However, it is important to consider other aspects such as personal abilities, market conditions, and networking possibilities.

Further research is warranted to delve deeper into the intricacies of this relationship and its potential implications for policy and practice.

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